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**Expanding Long Term Financing Options for Middle-income Countries in Latin
America and Caribbean with High HIV Burden**

A Case Study from Guatemala

Draft Submitted by

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Abstract

A model was developed to project future demand and supply of financing for Guatemala's HIV/AIDS programs under different scenarios over a 15 year period, from 2009 to 2023. The exercise reveals that in all likelihood Guatemala will face large and growing funding gaps in the future, and those new funding sources or a growing fiscal effort by government, or sustained or greater financial support from donors will be required to bridge such gaps.

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Acronyms

AIDS	Acquired immune deficiency syndrome
ARV	Antiretroviral therapy
BSS	Behavioral surveillance survey
CBO	Community Based Organizations
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, DHSS (USA)
CSW	Commercial sex worker
DHS	Demographic health survey
H(M)IS	Health (Management) Information System
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
IDU	Injecting drug user
IEC	Information, education, communication
IPT	Intermittent preventive treatment
IRS	Indoor residual spraying
KAP	Knowledge, Attitude and Practice
M&E	Monitoring and evaluation
MARP	Most-at-risk population (female sex workers, clients of female sex workers, injecting drug users and men who have sex with men)
MDG	Millennium Development Goal
METAT	Monitoring and Evaluation Technical Assistance and Training
MICS	Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys
MOH	Ministry of Public Health
MSM	Men who have sex with men
NAP	National AIDS Program
NASA	National AIDS Spending Assessment
NGO	Non-governmental organization
ODA	Official development assistance
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
OGAC	The President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief: Office of the Global AIDS Coordinator
OVC	Orphans and vulnerable children
PEPFAR	President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (USA)
PLWHA	People living with HIV/AIDS
PMTCT	Prevention of Mother-to-Child Transmission (of HIV)
PPM	Public-private mix
PSI	Population Services International
RNM	Resource needs model
SDA	Service delivery area
STI	Sexually transmitted infections
SW	Sex Workers
UNGASS	UN General Assembly Special Session
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
VCT	Voluntary counseling and testing

1. Introduction

The worldwide HIV/AIDS epidemic reached its peak in 1996, when 3.5 million new infections were reported, compared with 30 percent fewer new cases being reported in 2008. However, the number of people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) worldwide continued to grow in 2008, reaching an estimated 33.4 million, due to the number of new cases reported and the increase in life expectancy of people living with HIV/AIDS. The total number of PLWHA in 2008 was 20 percent higher than in 2000, and three times as high as in 1990 (UNAIDS, 2009a).

In 2008 the adult prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Latin America was 0.6 percent, below the global prevalence of 0.8 percent; conversely, in the Caribbean prevalence was higher at 1.0 percent. The Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) region as a whole reported a prevalence that was well below that of sub-Saharan Africa (5.2 percent) (UNAIDS, 2009a). Half of adults living with the virus are women. The latest epidemiological data suggest that the epidemic in Latin America remains stable.

The majority of countries in the region have prevalence rates of less than 1 percent, but the prevalence among specific groups, such as men who have sex with men (MSM) and sex workers (SW), is often very high. The most severe expressions of the epidemic occur in smaller countries such as Belize, Guyana, and Suriname, with prevalence ranging between 2.1 and 2.5 percent. For example, in the Bahamas and Haiti more than 2 percent of the adult population is living with HIV/AIDS. Higher prevalence rates are found only in sub-Saharan Africa, making the Caribbean the second-most affected region in the world. Table 1 depicts the situation of the epidemic in terms of the estimated number of PLWHA, deaths and the lethality rate in selected Latin America and Caribbean countries.

Table 1 People living with HIV/AIDS and deaths from this cause in LAC region, circa 2006

Country	Living with HIV/AIDS (LWHA)		Estimated deaths due to HIV/AIDS, 2007	Lethality: Number of deaths/ Number of PLWHA (%)
	All people	Adult (15-49) rate %		
Brazil	730,000	0.6	15,000	2.1
Costa Rica	9,700	0.4	<200	2.1
Chile	31,000	0.3	<1,000	3.2
Average Latin America	1,700,000	0.5	63,000	3.7
Peru	76,000	0.5	3,300	4.3
Argentina	120,000	0.5	5,400	4.5
Ecuador	26,000	0.3	1,200	4.6
Paraguay	21,000	0.6	<1,000	4.8
El Salvador	35,000	0.8	1,700	4.9
Panama	20,000	1.0	<1,000	5.0
Uruguay	10,000	0.6	<500	5.0
Mexico	200,000	0.3	11,000	5.5
Belize	3,600	2.1	<200	5.6
Colombia	170,000	0.6	9,800	5.8
Bolivia	8,100	0.2	<500	6.2
Haiti	120,000	2.2	7,500	6.3
Dominican Republic	62,000	1.1	3,900	6.3
Honduras	28,000	0.7	1,800	6.4
Nicaragua	7,700	0.2	<500	6.5
Guatemala	59,000	0.8	3,900	6.6
Guyana	13,000	2.5	<1,000	7.7

Source: UNAIDS (2008).

According to the World Bank (2003), worldwide concern over the HIV/AIDS epidemic is large due to its triple impact on society:

- It destroys human capital, including accumulated life experience, job skills and knowledge.
- It weakens the mechanisms that generate human capital information, damaging the transmission of knowledge and potential productive capacity across generations.
- It makes investment in the education of children less attractive given the prospect that they may get infected, even if both parents remain uninfected.

A country's ability to fight the epidemic critically depends on the amount of resources it can mobilize to prevent and treat cases. Hence countries should establish the importance of measuring financing needs and resources availability. Success factors in managing the HIV/AIDS epidemic include:

- The existence of national health care organizations.
- The availability and allocation of public funds.
- The availability and allocation of international funds.
- The presence and strength of national initiatives and organizations around HIV/AIDS.

LAC countries have, with few exceptions (most notably Brazil), chosen the social security approach to achieve universal health care coverage. But a high prevalence of poverty, unemployment, and informal employment has restricted social security coverage to the relatively small share of the population in the formal sector of the economy. Given the epidemiological dynamics of the HIV/AIDS epidemic, it is expected that there will be an increasing demand for fresh resources each year. Social security institutions typically do not have enough resources to deal with the epidemic and therefore additional public, private, and international resources are necessary.

Despite resource limitations, the regional coverage of curative and preventive care for HIV/AIDS is relatively high in LAC compared with the rest of the developing world. UNAIDS (2009a) reports the following:

Antiretroviral coverage in Latin America (at 54% in 2008) is above the global average, with especially high coverage achieved in several upper-middle-income countries (World Health Organization, United Nations Children's Fund, UNAIDS, 2009). In general, treatment coverage is higher in South America than in Central America.

In 2008 per capita income in Guatemala, measured in international dollars, was US\$ 4,690, well below the LAC average of US\$ 10,159. The economic and HIV/AIDS situation in Guatemala could be summarized as follows:

- An economy highly dependent on agricultural exports, remittances and tourism, and thus, heavily affected by the international financial crisis;
- A very low tax-to-GDP ratio (about 10%) due to high levels of tax avoidance and tax evasion, which impact in low levels of public expenditure;
- A small share of public expenditure devoted to health care (about 8% of the public expenditure);
- A very limited coverage of social security (IGSS covers 25% of the economically active population, 11% of the total population, but a third of the people living with AIDS receiving ART);

- A late start for public funding of AIDS response (since 2002) but growing very rapidly, from less than USD 1 million in 2002 to USD 8 million in 2009;
- A very recent expansion of services in geographical terms (from the capital city to secondary cities) but also in programmatic issues (to intensify response to most-at-risk populations), as a result of the Global Fund grant starting in 2004 and recently approved extension for up to six more years;
- A series of silent geographical areas due to limited capacities for screening and diagnosis, in rural and indigenous areas of the country.

Whereas prevalence of HIV/AIDS in Guatemala is higher than average, the coverage of ARV, at 69 percent in 2008, was below the regional average (UNAIDS, 2009c). Securing adequate financing, both domestically and internationally, to fund HIV/AIDS in Guatemala is a priority concern of its government and of international agencies such as UNAIDS.

2. Study goal, objectives, and products

The goal of this study is to insinuate a sustainable long term financial strategy to respond to the HIV/AIDS epidemic in Latin American countries. This document endeavors to examine the financial feasibility of the HIV/AIDS programs and interventions in Guatemala. It is hoped that the lessons drawn from this country report may help other developing countries develop their own long-term financing strategy.

Report objectives are as follows:

- Identify existing financing sources for Guatemala's national HIV/AIDS program.
- Gather the program's service delivery objectives, both for preventive and curative interventions, and also for coverage and access to HIV/AIDS care.
- Estimate resource needs for 2018-2023 in a range between a low- and a high-needs scenario.
- Calculate the potential gap in relation to needs and required expenditure.
- Recommend sustainable measures to meet financing needs.
- Estimate the economic impact on the country.
- Identify best practices and / or innovative financing mechanisms that could be adapted in other regions.

The methodology used in this case study is the same developed for the Dominican Republic and Ecuador.

This report focuses on designing a model for demand and supply of funding for HIV/AIDS in Guatemala and on determining any future gaps in financing for the period 2010-2023. These results will be presented to decision makers in the country to generate a debate regarding the feasibility of implementation for the proposed scenarios and the identification of new funding sources to fill any of the projected gaps.

3. Literature review

Projecting the costs and funding for HIV/AIDS response poses several methodological problems, three of which are considered particularly relevant for this effort and are therefore addressed in this section. First, the epidemiological data from various sources show disparate

results, which mean an additional difficulty in the identification of the necessary resources related to the demand scenarios.

Second, there is international evidence that the epidemic may affect a country's present and future income flow, and that this may undermine the country's ability to collect taxes and finance social programs, such as HIV/AIDS. If this were to happen in Guatemala, then a model that projects public financing into the future should take into account the relationship between the epidemic and income, and the associated future drop in public funds resulting from the epidemic. Third, the projection of costs of preventive and curative interventions must reflect the behavior of costs as coverage expands over time. It may be the case that as coverage expands of some HIV/AIDS programs (for example, the delivery of ARV) total costs would increase but less than proportionally owing to possible economies of scale in the purchase and delivery of these drugs. Other interventions may also face economies of scale, or diseconomies of scale, where total costs increase more than proportionally with coverage. Third, the efficiency of delivery may improve or worsen with time. For example, current management costs may be reduced to more efficient levels that are consistent with the international practice, or the procurement of input, such as condoms, may be made more transparent through international tenders, hence lowering their unit cost.

It is important to take these three effects into account when developing the model to project future costs and financing. What follows is a review of the international literature on these issues.

3.1. The social and economic costs of HIV/AIDS

The prospect that the HIV/AIDS epidemic may affect economic growth is a central concern in this study which projects the future needs and availability of financing for HIV/AIDS interventions. If higher disease prevalence lowers economic output then it may negatively affect government tax revenue and its ability to finance social programs, such as the prevention and treatment of HIV/AIDS. If such a downward spiral exists, then an economic forecast model should take it into account to predict with accuracy the future availability of government financing. Haacker (2009) clearly explains this as follows:

The most visible fiscal consequences of HIV/AIDS include increased spending on prevention, care, and treatment, but the fiscal implications go far beyond this. As economic growth declines, the domestic tax base weakens and domestic revenues fall.

Will the countries that are the subject of the present study – the Dominican Republic, Ecuador and Guatemala– experience, as a consequence of HIV/AIDS, a future drop in economic growth? And will such a drop significantly reduce the tax base and therefore the availability of government revenue to finance interventions in health in general, in HIV/AIDS in particular, and in other social programs?

Several studies have estimated the long-term consequences of the HIV/AIDS epidemic on economic growth. Their findings may shed some light on this issue in the case of Latin America and the Caribbean. UNAIDS (2004), Haacker (2009), and Stover and Bollinger (1999) summarize the results from several of them. While all of these authors mention that the empirical evidence is mixed and at times contradictory, they gather results from different studies and conclude that with all probability there is a negative relationship between the extent of the epidemic and economic growth.

Figure 1 presents selected results in the form of an estimated interval per country or group of countries from sub-Saharan Africa. It shows that in Botswana the epidemic could be responsible for an annual drop in per capita income varying from a low of 0.8 percent to a high as 1.6 percent. For a group of 30 countries from the region, the annual drop in per capita income would be between zero percent (no impact) and 0.6 percent.

Figure 1 Selected countries from Sub-Saharan Africa: Annual drop in per capita GNP attributable to HIV/AIDS epidemic (percent)

Source: UNAIDS (2004), Haacker (2009), Over (1992), Stover and Bollinger (1999).

Figure 2 Selected countries from sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America: HIV/AIDS prevalence population ages 15-49 (%)

The influence of the HIV/AIDS epidemic on economic output no doubt increases with its severity, although the exact relationship cannot easily be established empirically. In 2004 the HIV/AIDS prevalence in Botswana was as high as 25 percent, the highest among the countries included in the above figure. The estimated impact on economic growth was also highest for that country. Around the same year the average prevalence for the group of 30 sub-Saharan countries was about 3 percent. For these countries, since 1992, it was estimated that the influence of the epidemic on economic growth was an annual reduction as high as 0.6 percent.

Countries from Latin America and the Caribbean exhibit HIV/AIDS prevalence rates that are generally much lower than those of countries in sub-Saharan Africa. This can be seen in Figure 2. Prevalence in the study countries varies from a low of 0.19 percent in Ecuador to a high of 0.63 percent in the Dominican Republic. It is therefore expected that in the countries selected

for the current study any detrimental consequences of HIV/AIDS on economic output and public finances will be very low, if any. Therefore it does not seem necessary to model such an effect, because of its small expected magnitude, and it may not be possible to do so because the empirical estimates available in the literature come from countries with very different expressions of the epidemic.

But the HIV/AIDS epidemic has economic and social consequences that go beyond the loss of output. In the document "The economic costs of AIDS", based mainly on the situation of African countries, the World Bank Group (2003) discusses the loss of human capital resulting from the epidemic. It states that most studies about the macro-economic consequences of HIV/AIDS attempt to measure the impact as a reduction of GDP but fail to address one of the main factors affecting economic growth, namely human capital. HIV/AIDS affects economic growth by the devastating combination of several factors that destroy human capital. As a disease mainly of young adults, it selectively destroys human capital by wiping out their life experience, work skills, and knowledge gained over the years. It also weakens and reduces human capital formation mechanisms. Specifically, the death of one or both parents of young children weakens the transmission of knowledge and the joint productive capacity of families. Additionally, the drop in income that follows the death of one parent or both of them reduces the amount of resources available for the education of surviving children. Furthermore, the possibility that children will get the disease in adulthood makes investment in their education less attractive. With less education and knowledge transmitted from parents to children, as well as deprivation of love and guidance from childhood, the children of HIV/AIDS victims who later become adults are less able to raise their own children and invest in their education. The effects of this process are only noticeable over the long-term and poor education of children today results in low productivity of the adult a generation later.

It falls beyond the scope and possibilities of the current study to model the economic and social consequences just discussed. In judging the various results, however, it is important to keep these consequences in mind.

3.2. Economies of scale in the production and delivery of HIV/AIDS interventions

The current exercise involves the projection over time, through the year 2023, of the costs of curative and preventive interventions, both individual and collective, to deal with HIV/AIDS in Guatemala. It is difficult to project future costs of health services, even if one knows with some certainty what will be the future volume of services to be delivered. For example, suppose that the government had plans to double by the year 2023, to 80 percent, the current coverage of 40 percent of ARVs. Given the large share of HIV/AIDS spending accounted for by ARV therapy in the country, it is crucial to predict what will be the future resource needs of this important cost item as future coverage expands. Will the total costs of ARVs also double along with coverage? Or will total costs grow more than proportionally or less than proportionally with coverage? To answer these questions it is useful to look at past costs and their relationship with coverage in the country, to check, for example, whether the increase of coverage, from 20 percent to 40 percent, resulted in more or less the same proportion in spending. Also, projecting future costs requires knowledge about the future costs of inputs (will pharmaceutical companies raise or lower the prices of ARVs? Will they provide further volume discounts?), the future costs of management (will management costs of the ARV procurement facility have to double when

coverage doubles? Will staff salaries increase annually irrespective of coverage?), and other future costs.

The international evidence on the economies of scale in the delivery of ARVs should, in principle, help predict what could happen to total costs in Guatemala as coverage of ARVs expands. Evidence from Nigeria and Brazil is presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4 below. Kombe *et al.* (no date, around 2007, Figure 3) examined the cost structure of ARV programs in Nigeria, including the costs of human resources, medicines, monitoring tests, and capital and training. Their aim was to predict future variations in costs associated with coverage expansion. Thus, their study was prospective. They concluded that a considerable expansion in coverage would more or less maintain average cost per patient covered constant, at around US\$ 700 per covered patient per year.

Nunn *et al.* (2007) carried out a retrospective study to explain the variation in total and average costs of Brazil's universal and publicly funded ARV program. They found that between 2001 and 2004 the average annual cost per patient covered dropped considerably, from US\$ 1,945 to US\$ 1,297, but then it doubled through the next year (Figure 4). The number of patients covered increased throughout the period. The major driver of cost increases in Brazil was increased purchase quantities of six specific patented drugs and a locally produced generic. A decline in prices for many of the patented drugs that constitute the largest share of drug costs meant that nearly the entire increase in overall drug expenditures between 2001 and 2005 was attributable to increases in drug quantities. Had all drug quantities been held constant from 2001 until 2005, total costs would have increased by only an estimated US\$7 million. In the absence of price declines for patented drugs, Brazil would have spent over twice as much, or US\$2 billion on ARV drugs between 2001 and 2005, implying a savings of US\$1.2 billion from price declines. They also found that Brazilian prices for locally produced generic ARVs were generally much higher than the lowest international prices meeting global pharmaceutical quality standards. The prices of Brazil's locally produced generics had risen in Brazil while declining globally. As a consequence, Brazil had spent an excess US\$ 110 million by producing local generics instead of purchasing them in international markets.

Figure 3 Nigeria: Patients receiving ARVs and average annual cost of ARVs per patient, year 2007 and projected

Source: Kombe *et al.* (circa 2007).

Figure 4 Brazil: Patients receiving highly active antiretroviral therapy (HAART) and average annual cost of ARVs per patient, 1997-2006

Source: Nunn *et al.* (2007).

When the average cost *per unit of output* (for example, per patient receiving ARV therapy) drops as output expands, economists say that they are in the presence of *economies of scale*. That is a desirable situation from the perspective of financing, because each person covered, or each unit of service delivered, will *on average* cost less. So a doubling of coverage will result in less than a doubling in the associated costs. This implies that the larger the program, the smaller the amount of resources that will be required to pay for each person covered, or patient seen, or output delivered.

Kumaranayake (2008) reviewed economic methodologies to generate a conceptual framework for classifying existing data on the costs of scaling up HIV/AIDS programs, looking at both short-run and long-run perspectives. She found that there is growing evidence of scale variation among the costs of HIV/AIDS interventions, and that it may explain 26-70 percent of cost variation across locations for similar interventions. Average costs may become larger or smaller as the volume of services expands (as was the case in Brazil's ARV program between 2001 and 2005), depending on the level of coverage and type of intervention. Key constraints to scaling up include infrastructure investments. She concluded that the available evidence suggests that cost efficiencies associated with scale may reflect different ways of delivering services at higher volumes and also variations in quality. But she concluded that there is a very limited economic evidence base and mechanisms to integrate economic analyses into routine program monitoring are recommended.

Table 2 Evidence from the literature about economies of scale in HIV/AIDS programs

Program	Description	Findings
Vertical transmission	Empirical cost of 15 programs in India	The variation in scale explains 42% of the variation in average cost
VCT	Malawi. Empirical econometric analysis of costs of VCT, data over 34 months	Customers range from 200 to 1600 per month; fixed costs range from 9% to 21% Significant economies of scale estimated rate 1.5. Changes in the production function
VCT	India. VCT 17 empirical cost data, more than 12 months.	334-7802 clients per site per year. Fixed costs average 12.4% of total annual costs. The variation in the cost per customer is assigned 73% to scale
VCT	South Africa. Cost rapid empirical test 1 Clinical data of 12 months.	662 customers in 1 year, costs decrease by 66% in months of greater burden, suggesting economies of scale
Prevention activities in targeted population"	India. Empirical cost of 15 prevention programs among sex workers, more than 12 months.	Range TS 803-6379. 5.2-8.3% fixed costs (rent, capital). Significant relationship between the scale and size of the program, suggesting economies of scale. Finding of reduced time to be the largest program
Prevention activities in targeted population"	India. Empirical cost of 17 prevention programs in TS. More than one year	Range TS 205-2008. Fixed costs 13-40% (median 15%). 50% of the variation in the average cost attributed to the scale, controlling factors - different production functions Nonparametric analysis shows average cost curve in U, with the minimum average cost occurring in the size of TS 1500 year
Prevention activities in targeted population"	India. Empirical cost in 15 districts, over 24,000 sex workers in more than 18 months	Fixed costs range from 11 to 32% of the total cost. Sevenfold reduction in the average cost per TS on a scale of activities by district TS 3000. Threefold reduction in average costs for projects started later
Prevention activities in targeted population""	India. Econometric analysis of 78 prevention projects funded by the state and TS 16 projects, more than 12 months	Analysis of expenditure data shows that economies of scale were not exhausted, a fall of 0.002% in the total cost for each person served. The estimation using TS data show an efficiency point on the scale 1,750-2,000 people served, approximately
Prevention activities in targeted population"	India, Russia and South Africa. Empirical cost of TS 40 programs	The scale explains 38-88% of the variation in average costs. Decrease in average costs, not increase
Prevention activities in	Russia. Empirical cost of 22 projects to	The scale accounts for 45% of the variation in costs. Turn

Table 2 Evidence from the literature about economies of scale in HIV/AIDS programs

Program	Description	Findings
targeted population"	UDI	the scale is associated with a 34.5% reduction in average costs
Treatment of STDs	Thailand. Empirical analysis of incremental costs of STDs	The expansion of evening hours of care in STI clinics in 2000 allows processing of additional clients at 31 dol.
Treatment of STDs	Cambodia. Empirical cost of STDs interventions, a period longer than 3 years	The number of annual visits increased 3 times from 4,369 to 13,329 and the cost per visit was reduced to almost half. The decrease is attributed to the large increase in visits
Treatment of STDs	Econometric analysis of average costs of STDs obtained from 53 studies	The scale range is from 3 to 63,693 people a year. The estimates show a small but significant scale effect suggesting that unit costs decrease with scale
Treatment of STDs	India. Empirical cost analysis in 12 districts, reaching more than 20,000 TS, more than 18 months	The average cost per person treated per district was 27 dol. and there was a six fold reduction in average costs by increasing the level of care for patients in more than 1400 patients per district
Treatment of STDs	India, Mexico, Russia	There is a modest effect on the scale with an explanation of 42-70% of costs for the change of the scale. It shows an increase in average costs
VCT, ITS, condom social marketing, IEC	Uganda. Empirical cost randomized over 4 years	Various interventions to 96,000 individuals within communities. An increase of 74% led to a 34% reduction in average cost, suggesting scale effects
IEC	Mexico. Empirical cost of 22 programs	The scale variation explains a proportion of 91%, doubling the scale is a 64% reduction in average costs
Prevention activities in targeted population"	34 sub-Saharan countries. Scale econometric analysis of program costs, to pursue the relationship between the infrastructure of health systems and scale to an increase of 25% coverage	Marginal costs are higher than average cost, suggesting diseconomies of scale. A 25% increase in marginal costs is approximately 7 times higher in care and care for prevention

According to Kumaranayake (2008), there is evidence of economies (or diseconomies) of scale in HIV/AIDS interventions. Interventions with small proportions of fixed costs such as VCT and IEC exhibit declining average costs as the scale of activity expands, so it is economically optimal to run larger programs. At the other extreme, interventions related to health benefits (STI or prevention of transmission from mother to child) are likely to face diseconomies of scale and the U-shape of their average cost curves suggests that there is an optimum size for such programs. The above table summarizes the author's findings regarding the relationship between scale and total or average costs.

3.3. Improvements in efficiency

Stover et al. (2006) find that a strong, global expanded commitment to prevention programs targeted at sexual transmission and transmission among injecting drug users could avert 28 million new worldwide HIV infections between 2005 and 2015. This figure is more than half of the new infections that might otherwise occur during that period in 125 low-and middle-income countries. Although preventing infections, this new investment would require about US\$ 122 billion over this period and would reduce future needs for treatment and care. The analysis suggests that it will cost about US\$ 3,900 to prevent each new infection, but it will produce savings of US\$ 4,700 in forgone treatment costs. Thus, greater spending on prevention not only would prevent more than half the new infections that would occur from 2005 and 2015, but it would produce a net financial saving as future costs for treatment and care are averted. The figures for the LAC region are as follows: prevention of one case costs US\$ 5,045; present savings and treatment costs averted are US\$ 12,330.

Box 1. HIV/AIDS epidemic and response in LAC region

In Latin America and the Caribbean as a whole, the HIV/AIDS epidemic does not have the alarming proportions of sub-Saharan Africa, where the adult prevalence was about 5.2 percent in 2008 (UNAIDS, 2009a). Yet the Caribbean exhibits the second highest level of adult HIV/AIDS prevalence outside of sub-Saharan Africa (about 1.0 percent), and Haiti is the hardest hit country in this region, with an adult prevalence of 2.2 percent of the population. In the LAC region prevalence is not linked with income, as can be seen in Figure 5. Bolivia, which is nearly as poor as Haiti, has a prevalence that is below the regional average and only a fraction of Haiti's. Trinidad & Tobago, the richest country in LAC, has the third highest prevalence. In LAC there is a slightly negative relationship between national income and total spending on HIV/AIDS (including public and private domestic and international resources; Figure 7). The Dominican Republic and Ecuador, two of the three countries selected for this study, exhibit lower total spending than would be expected given their income, whereas Guatemala spends about what one would predict given its income. In addition, in LAC the combined spending on HIV/AIDS, expressed as a proportion of national income, increases with prevalence, implying that the countries with a more severe epidemic devote a greater share of own and international resources to fight it (

Figure 5 Prevalence of HIV/AIDS, % population 15-49b

Figure 8 and

Figure 9).

Figure 6 Total HIV/AIDS spending as % of GNI

Figure 7 Total HIV/AIDS spending as % of GNI, excluding Haiti

Figure 8 Prevalence of HIV/AIDS, % population 15-49

Figure 9 Prevalence of HIV/AIDS, % population 15-49, excluding Haiti

4. Current situation in Guatemala

4.1. Demographic and epidemiologic data

The first case of AIDS in Guatemala was reported in 1984. The epidemic has been in the country for 26 years now, although 63% of cases have appeared during the last five-year period.

- *Population:* In 2009 total population in Guatemala was 14.0 million. The World Bank (2008) projects that it will reach 19.2 million people by 2023, with total growth of 37 percent in the period.
- *Population HIV/AIDS:* By the end of 2009 there were 20,473 reported cases in the country out of an estimated total population living with HIV/AIDS of 61,500 (for a notification rate of 33.3 percent). The total population prevalence was 0.4% in 2009.
- *HIV/AIDS case fatality rate:* The reported case fatality rate among HIV/AIDS patients was 6.6 percent during 2007.

In Guatemala, 20,473 HIV/AIDS cases have been reported since the epidemic first appeared in 1984 up to December 2009. Masculinity ratio is 1.68, considerably varying in different age groups. Under 29 years old, it ranges from 1.01 to 1.68; between 30 and 59 years old, it goes from 2.07 to 2.27; and from 60 years and more, it varies from 3.42 to 6.29 infected men per woman.

Sexual transmission was reported in 94% of the reported cases; mother-to-child transmission, in 5.11%. Other ways of transmission account for 0.09% of reported cases. Two-thirds of the reported cases occur among people between 20 and 39 years of age. During those years, a grant from Global Fund was implemented, the spatial coverage of services increased, awareness, detection and treatment of infections scaled up.

The epidemic is concentrated in most-at-risk populations. Whereas prevalence in the adult population (15-49) in 2009 was 0.79%, among men who have sex with men it reached 18.3%, people with tuberculosis, 12.9%, people deprived of liberty, 3.4%, youth at social risk, 3.3%, female sex workers, 1.09%, pregnant women, 0.33%. However, prevalence rates have increased in all departments, but especially in those having the largest urban centres, with lower socioeconomic conditions, and located at entry points or along the routes connecting the country's borders (MSPAS, 2010. Country Progress Report UNGASS 2010).

In addition, in departments with higher HIV rates, people between 18 and 49 years old represent at least 45% of the total, which means a lower dependency rate, but on the other hand, more people of reproductive age exposed to sexual transmission.

4.2. Facing the epidemic

According to the Health Sector Law,² the steering role is competence of the MOH. This is confirmed by the AIDS General Act,³ which defines as the MOH's role, executed through the

² Decree 90-97 Health Code.

³ Decree 27-2000 General Act to combat HIV/AIDS, art. 4

National AIDS Program, to “coordinate and supervise” actions in the national response. This specific law also creates the National Multisectoral Commission (NMC) on AIDS, with public sector, private sector and civil society representatives.⁴ The NMC mandate consists of planning, executing and evaluating health programs related to HIV/AIDS and STIs, and fund-raising to complement public funds, among others.

However, due to regulations from the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria, a parallel organization called the “Country Coordinating Mechanism” was developed. The CCM have exerted more of the steering (with a strong presence of the NAP in it) than NMC. An attempt to revive the NMC lasted less than six months.

Regulation in AIDS is also competence of the NAP. However, due to the high fragmentation of the health system, private providers, IGSS and the MOH have technical standards of their own. In recent years, progress has been achieved in harmonizing protocols and norms.

The country’s legal framework also has inner contradictions. The AIDS General Act bans HIV tests as a job requisite, but the Work Code establishes that any worker has to demonstrate that he or she is not bearer of contagious disease, and so asking for HIV testing is permitted.

The health system comprises three major subsystems of providers:⁵

- **Central government services:** Tax funded services, mainly provided by the Ministry of Health (MOH), except for two hospitals: one for the military (Ministry of Defense) and the police (Ministry of Interior). At the community level, tax funded services operate through a network of NGOs delivering basic services. Anyone can visit public facilities, even insured people, and user-fees are banned.
- **Social security:** Financed through payroll taxes, the system is mandatory to all formal employers, including public sector workers. The Guatemalan Institute of Social Security (IGSS) has its own provision network of health facilities, but also purchases services from private providers. About one fifth of the economically active population is covered by the IGSS, which has not devised any programs for informal sector workers.
- **Private provision:** It is mainly funded by direct out-of-pocket payments (65% of total health expenditure) but also by private insurance plans. Growing at a fast pace, this subsector is poorly regulated and less supervised. People at all socioeconomic levels utilize private provided services, even the IGSS affiliated workers. Private prepaid plans are only 4.4% of the private expenditure, and the rest is OOP.

⁴ Op. cit. arts. 6-7

⁵ PAHO (2007). Health System Profile: Guatemala 2007. Third Edition.

4.3. Economic and financing data

In Guatemala, total health expenditure (THE) is 7% of the GDP. Public sources cover 29.7% of these expenses and 70.7% come from private sources. External sources have a small share of 1.4% of THE.⁶

- *Per capita income:* Guatemala has a per capita income of 4,760 (PPP, international dollars).
- *Health expenditure as % of GDP:* Guatemala spends a 7% of its GDP on health, equivalent to 259 (PPP, international dollars) per capita. The public expenditure is 29.7% of the total expenditure on health (THE).
- *Expenditure on HIV/AIDS during 2008:* In 2008 Guatemala reported spending a total of USD 51.3 million on HIV/AIDS, of which 56 percent were from public sources, just 8 percent from private domestic sources, and 36 percent from international sources. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** *Per capita AIDS health expenditure/total population:* Per capita AIDS health expenditure/total population is 1.4 dollars, equivalent to 0.5% of total expenditure on health.

Between 2004 and 2009 total expenditure on AIDS has increased 2.5 times (see Figure 10).

Figure 10 HIV/AIDS sources of financing, 2004-2009 (percentage)

Source: preliminary NASA 2010

Financial sources for the HIV/AIDS response in Guatemala include taxes, social security contributions, donations and out-of-pocket expenditures.

⁶ WHO (2010). **World Health Statistics**. Table 7: Health Expenditure, pp. 132-3.

Figure 11 HIV/AIDS expenditure by categories, 2004-2009 (percentage)

Source: preliminary NASA 2010.

General taxes cover central government expenses, which includes the NAP budget, MOH facilities budgets, current transfers to NGOs providing long term care and social care, as well as resources for prevention and treatment for army and police forces.

The Guatemalan Social Security Institute (in Spanish, IGSS) collects payroll taxes from employers and employees of the formal sector. The informal sector represents almost three fourths of the economically active population, and that is the major reason for a constricted coverage of social security. Even when other schemes have been studied and proposed, IGSS has not considered alternative plans for self-employed individuals, peasants and informal workers. However, IGSS was the first funding agency allowing antiretroviral treatment. About a third of PLWHA currently receiving ART are covered with IGSS funding.

External sources are relevant to AIDS response funding in Guatemala. Bilateral cooperation includes aid from the Netherlands and United States of America; multilateral sources are UNAIDS, UNICEF and the Global Fund. International NGOs also contribute: ActionAid, Caritas, Catholic Relief Services, Red Cross, Plan International, Soros Foundation, among others.

Out-of-pocket expenditures are estimated to be up to 7.7% of the total AIDS expenditure in Guatemala, according to the NASA exercise, which is about to be completed. Other private sources, such as business contributions, are very rare in Guatemala.

4.4. Uses of resources

In 2008 Guatemala reported a total HIV/AIDS spending of about USD 51.3 million, of which 56 percent were from public sources. The allocation of spending is shown in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**; 62% of all resources were devoted to treatment and an additional 25% to prevention.

The following table summarizes the expenditure by source of financing and allocation in year 2008:

Table 3 Sources of HIV/AIDS financing and categories of spending, 2008 (percentage)

Spending category	Sources of financing			Total
	Public	Private	External	
Prevention	28.4	22.9	48.7	24.5
Care and treatment	75.4	3.3	21.3	62.2
Orphans and vulnerable children	99.3	0.0	0.7	0.1
Program management	21.6	0.1	78.3	11.8
Human resources	0.6	0.0	99.4	0.4
Favorable environment	2.5	2.6	94.8	0.3
HIV/AIDS research	0.7	0.0	99.3	0.6
Total	56.6	7.7	35.8	100.0

Source: preliminary NASA 2010.

The allocation of funds to the various spending categories was as follows:

- *Prevention*: 49 percent of spending was financed by international funds, while public funds accounted for 28 percent of the total.
- *Care and treatment*: Public sources accounted for the largest share of spending (75 percent), while private sources accounted for 3 percent.
- *Orphans and vulnerable children*: It was financed almost entirely by public funds (99 percent), with no private sector input.
- *Management and Program Management*: It was financed by international sources (78 percent) and public funds (22 percent).
- *Human resources*: It was financing almost entirely from international funds (99 percent).
- *Social protection and social services*: 40 percent of this item was paid for by international funds and the rest by public funds.
- *Enabling environment*: International sources paid for 95 percent of this spending category.
- *Research related to HIV*: 72.36 percent was financed by international funds and only 1 percent by public funds.

In the largest expenditure categories, public funding was directed primarily toward treatment (US\$24.0 million). International and private funds went primarily toward prevention and treatment.

Between 2003 and 2008 total HIV/AIDS financing increased every year, with a total growth of 182 percent.

The greatest financing growth was during the years 2006 and 2007, reaching a growth of 4 percent each year. During 2006, the largest finance growth was in private funds with an increase of 190 percent over the previous year.

4.5. Stakeholders

This part of the report includes an analysis of information collected to determine which stakeholders might have an interest in the HIV/AIDS epidemic in Guatemala. This project involved travel to the country to analyze these possible actors.

Stakeholder analysis involves a review of the following issues that contribute to the formulation and implementation of policies:

- Resources: human, financial, technological, and other resources available to the stakeholder and his or her ability to mobilize them
- Interest: reflects the degree to which the stakeholder might support or oppose specific efforts or initiatives
- Power: ability to affect specific efforts or initiatives
- Leadership: the willingness to initiate, steer, or lead an action. Establishing whether or not the stakeholder has leadership will help those interested in bridging gaps between financing and resource needs target those stakeholders who will be more likely to take active steps to support or oppose needed action (and convince others to do so).

In summary, this analysis is necessary to understand if present and future actors will maintain/increase/decrease the technical, social or financial support for the program in a long term scenario.

B&A will develop a list of stakeholders in coordination with UNAIDS and Guatemala's agents. A draft list of key actors includes:

- National AIDS Program
- Country Coordinating Mechanism
- UNAIDS
- USAID Program to Strengthen AIDS Response in Central America (PASCA)
- Asociación Gente Positiva (Positive People Association)
- Guatemalan Social Security Institute (IGSS)
- Ministry of Health (MSPAS)

This list should be reviewed by the Global Fund in Geneva, given that there is no local, in-country representation and they are the key funder.

5. Methods

This section describes the model built to project spending and financing of HIV/AIDS interventions in Guatemala, the model's assumptions and the data sources.

5.1. Model description

This section begins with an overview of the logic of the HIV/AIDS financing gap model, followed by a description of the methods used to forecast the epidemic. Next it explains how the associated prevention and treatment costs were drawn in the model, and then presents the assumptions made to predict financing. Finally, it shows how financing gaps are estimated.

Overview: The model separately projects the demand for resources for HIV/AIDS interventions, including promotive, preventive, and curative activities, and the supply of resources coming from government, households, and donors (see Figure 12). The demand for resources is the projected costs of HIV/AIDS interventions. The supply of resources is the projected financing. A comparison of demand and supply, for each year of the projected horizon, indicates whether there is a gap in financing (demand > supply) or sufficient financing (demand = supply), or a surplus in financing (demand < supply). If there is a projected gap (as illustrated in

Figure 13) simulations can be carried out through the model to examine whether changes in targets or strategies can lower the demand for financing. Examples of changes in strategy would be an increase in program efficiency through measures such as the centralized purchasing of ARVs, or an increase in the supply of financing, for example through the use of new sources of financing.

Figure 12 Alternative hypothetical scenarios regarding the projected sufficiency of financing for HIV/AIDS at the country level

The authors made annual projections for the period 2009-2023 of both required resources (demand) for HIV/AIDS and allocated resources (supply). They formulated 3 scenarios each for demand and supply (base, optimistic, and pessimistic, all 6 described below in greater detail), giving rise to 9 combined scenarios. For each of these 9 scenarios the authors computed on an annual basis the expected financing gap (if any, if not the surplus) over the projected horizon 2009-2023. Projections of demand and supply are presented in an itemized fashion according to the categories defined in the country's NASA.

Epidemic: The trend of the epidemic was drawn through the year 2015 using official estimates made by national authorities. Beyond 2015 the authors adopted a phased approach based on the following six parameters that characterize the epidemic:

- Current and projected total population
- Reported cases
- Estimated cases
- Prevalence
- Underreporting
- Case fatality rate

The year 2008 was defined as the base year. The authors decided to use 2008 as the base year in this study to allow comparability with the two other study countries for which the most recent NASA data available are for 2008.

In 2008 the total population in the country was 13.6 million, the number of reported HIV/AIDS cases was 19,242, and the total estimated population living with HIV/AIDS was 60,243 people, for a rate of underreporting of 68 percent. The national prevalence was 0.4 percent. The model assumes a gradual reduction in underreporting to reflect a successful effort by the national HIV/AIDS authority to expand coverage.

Figure 13 Hypothetical scenario where an increase in program efficiency is used to breach the projected financing gap

Figure 14 Impact of alternative HIV/AIDS control strategies on prevalence: an illustrative hypothetical example

Whereas Guatemalan health authorities have their own, official projection of the course of the epidemic, these authors found it necessary to consider alternative scenarios for the epidemic to come up with an internally consistent model. Figure 15 compares the official projected path of the epidemic (upper curve) with a projection made by the authors fitting a logarithmical equation to the historic data for the period 2000-2008. As can be seen, the official projection is much more static. It is unlikely, despite an ever growing response, that we will see increases from year to year of 1,000 persons, as in the official projection. Since the authors of this report were unable to ascertain the basis for the official figures they decided to make their own base projection, represented by the lower curve, and use it in their various scenarios.

Figure 15 PLWHA: historic data (2000-2008) and projections (2009-2023)

The need to model the future number of cases instead of using a static projection aligns with the need to make the future incidence of HIV/AIDS endogenous to the model's parameters. For example, as is illustrated in Figure 14, the future course of the epidemic will vary relative to a baseline scenario if Guatemala adopts a more aggressive and therefore more effective strategy to treat PLWHA with ARVs, for example changing the CD4 count that triggers ARV treatment from 100 to 350. Such a change has two different and opposing consequences. First, it reduces incidence and this effect results in a drop in the number of PLWHA. Second, it reduces mortality among PLWHA, an effect that results in an increase in the number of PLWHA. The resulting net effect on the number of PLWHA will depend on the relative magnitude of these two effects. While the authors did not find empirical information from the literature regarding the effect of a change in the CD4 count policy on incidence, they did find a study indicating that when the coverage of ARV therapies increases from 50 percent to 75 percent and remains at this higher level over a 30-year period, incidence drops by 26 percent.⁷ This would reduce the number of new cases and therefore the total projected number of PLWHA. They also found that when the

⁷ Johnston KM et al. Expanding access to HAART: a cost-effective approach for treating and preventing HIV. AIDS, advance online publication: DOI:10. 1097/QAD.0bo13e32833af85d, 2010.

CD4 count is changed from 100 to 350, mortality among PLWHA drops by 6 percent each year.⁸ These two opposing effects were combined to project the number of PLWHA through 2023 in Guatemala.

5.2. Projections of demand for and supply of HIV/AIDS resources

In accordance with Guatemala’s NASA methodology, the model uses the following 8 spending categories.

- Prevention
- Care and treatment
- Orphans and vulnerable children
- Program management
- Human resources
- Social protection and social services
- Favorable environment
- HIV/AIDS research

To project costs the model considers that some costs vary according to projected activities (for example, ARV treatment costs, or the distribution of condoms, or the ambulatory or inpatient treatment of PLWHA) while some other costs are not associated with any specific coverage targets.

Target- related interventions. Guatemala aims at universal coverage of all PLWHA by 2015. Table 4 presents each intervention, its population coverage in 2008, and its projected coverage by the year 2015. It also shows the cost share of each intervention, where 100 percent is Guatemala’s total national spending on HIV/AIDS. The coverage rates achieved in 2015 are projected to remain constant through 2023. Current coverage rates were obtained from the most recent UNGASS report (2008-2009).

Table 4 Cost components for target-related interventions, cost share, current coverage (2008) and coverage targets (2015) (percent)

Spending category	Spending item	Spending share 2008	Coverage 2008	Coverage target 2015
Prevention	Prevention - Young people not attending school	0,1	22,5	75
	Prevention - Young people attending school	0,7	2,4	50
	Prevention of transmission of HIV for persons living with HIV	1,3	3,7	20
	Prevention of mother to child transmission	3,7	23,0	60
	Programs for men who have sex with men	1,3	75,3	95
	Programs for sex workers and their clients	3,2	92,7	95
	Blood safety	1,7	74,7	100
Treatment and care	Ambulatory patients	12,1	69,2	95
	First-line ARV	1,7	69,2	95
	Second-line ARV	0,1	69,2	95
	ARV therapy after failed second-line treatment	0,3	69,2	95
	ARV therapy in adults (total, not separated by treatment line)	17,9	69,2	95

⁸ (a) Life expectancy of individuals on combination antiretroviral therapy in high-income countries: a collaborative analysis of 14 cohort studies. The Antiretroviral Therapy Cohort Collaboration. The Lancet - 26 July 2008 (Vol. 372, Issue 9635, Pages 293 - 299). DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(08)61113-7 and (b) ARV treatment cuts mortality rate in early and late treaters. AIDS MEDS, January 5, 2010.

Total	44,1
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Source: NASA Guatemala 2010.

Once universal coverage is reached in 2015, the costs associated with the epidemic are modeled in proportion to either the total population growth or the growth in the PLWHA, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Variables in the determination of costs for target-related interventions, 2015-2023

Costs categories	Function – Details of Cost categories	PLWHA growth rate	Total population growth rate
Prevention	Prevention - Young people not attending school		X
	Prevention - Young people attending school		X
	Prevention of transmission of HIV for persons living with HIV	X	
	Prevention of mother to child transmission	X	
	Programs for men who have sex with men		X
	Programs for sex workers and their clients		X
	Blood safety		X
Care and treatment	Ambulatory patients	X	
	First-line ARV	X	
	Second-line ARV	X	
	ARV therapy after failed second-line treatment	X	
	ARV therapy in adults (total, not separated by treatment line)	X	

X indicates that the variable was used to determine the cost of the intervention.

Source: NASA Guatemala 2010.

No target interventions. Costs with no associated targets were calculated preserving their cost share of 2008, when they represented 55.9 percent of total HIV/AIDS costs in the country. The procedure to project these costs was as follows: first the model used actual spending information from 2008 to compute total target-related costs. Second, it assumed that these costs represented a constant 55.9 percent of total costs, as in 2008. Third, is computed the total spending amount dividing spending on the target-related costs by 44.1 percent. Fourth, to compute the cost of each spending item not linked to a target, it applied the cost share of that item in 2008 and shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Cost components and cost share for interventions not linked with coverage targets (2015) (%)

Spending category	Spending item	Spending share 2008 (%)	Projected annual growth through 2015
Program management	Administration and transaction costs associated with the management of funds	0.0	18,4
	Strengthening administration and management of programs (total, not by intervention type)	3.5	
	Operations research	0.1	18,4
	Infrastructure improvement and construction	0.0	18,4
	Monitoring and evaluation	0.0	18,4
	Planning, coordination and running of program	3.9	18,4
	Medication stock management system	0.0	0,0
	Supervision of personnel and patient tracking	0.0	18,4
	Information technology	0.0	18,4
	Obligatory testing of HIV (not VCT)	0.1	0,0
	Drug resistance vigilance	0.0	18,4
	Serologic vigilance	0.4	18,4
	Enabling environment	Strategic communication	0.5
Community development and environment improving to reduce vulnerability (total, not broken up by intervention)		0.5	18,4
Institutional development directly related to AIDS		0.4	18,4
Human rights program		0.2	18,4

Table 6 Cost components and cost share for interventions not linked with coverage targets (2015) (%)

Spending category	Spending item	Spending share 2008 (%)	Projected annual growth through 2015	
	Specific programs about AIDS aimed at women	2,6	18,4	
	Programs to reduce gender-based violence	0,0	0,0	
Orphans and vulnerable children	Community support	0,3	0,0	
	Support for families/homes for orphans and vulnerable children	2,9	18,4	
	Institutional care	1,5	0,0	
	Basic medical care for orphans and vulnerable children	4,2	18,4	
	Education for orphans and vulnerable children	0,0	18,4	
	Universal precautions	0,0	0,0	
	Services for orphans and vulnerable children (total)	0,1	0,0	
	Social services and administrative costs	0,0	0,0	
HIV Research	Biomedical research	0,0	0,0	
	Social science research	0,1	18,4	
	Clinical research	0,2	0,0	
	Epidemiological research	0,0	18,4	
	Total research about HIV	0,0	0,0	
	Vaccine research	0,0	0,0	
Prevention	Prevention activities, total	0,0	18,4	
	Male circumcision	0,0	18,4	
	Communication about health topics for social and behavior change	0,0	18,4	
	Voluntary testing and counseling	0,0	18,4	
	Safe medical injections	0,0	0,0	
	Safe medical injections	0,0	18,4	
	Social marketing of condoms	0,0	18,4	
	Microbicides	0,0	18,4	
	Community mobilization	0,0	18,4	
	Universal precautions	0,0	18,4	
	Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of STIs	0,0	18,4	
	Post-exposure prophylaxis	0,0	18,4	
	Workplace prevention programs	0,0	18,4	
	Programs to reduce harm for injecting drug users	0,6	0,0	
	Condom provision for men in the public and private sectors	0,0	18,4	
	Condom provision for women in the public and private sectors	0,0	0,0	
	Risk reduction in vulnerable communities	0,8	18,4	
	Social protection and social service	Income generation	0,0	0,0
		Social protection through monetary benefits	3,5	0,0
		Social protection through delivery of social services	0,5	18,4
Social protection through delivery of goods		0,0	18,4	
Social protection and social services, total		0,0	0,0	
Human resources	Formative education	3,0	18,4	
	Training	0,0	18,4	
	Monetary incentives for human resources	0,1	0,0	
	Human resources, total	0,0	0,0	
Treatment	Other caring and treatment services, total	1,0	18,4	
	Hospital treatment, total	0,3	18,4	
	Transport of patients and emergency rescue	0,2	18,4	
	Treatment of opportunistic infections	0,0	18,4	
Total		55.9		

Beyond 2015 costs not related to coverage targets were modeled in proportion to either the total population growth or the growth in the PLWHA, as is shown in Table 5. Costs not linked to targets were modeled in proportion. The same criterion used in categories and coverage targets is applied from 2016 onwards. In the case of interventions for PLWHA the epidemic growth rate was applied, whilst for the other interventions the total population growth rate was used. The parameter employed in every cost category is illustrated in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..**

Table 7 Variables intervening in the determination of costs for interventions not related to target, 2015-2023

Spending category	Spending item	PLWHA growth rate	Total population growth rate
Program management	Administration and transaction costs associated with the management of funds	X	
	Strengthening administration and management of programs (total, not by intervention type)	X	
	Operations research	X	
	Infrastructure improvement and construction	X	
	Monitoring and evaluation	X	
	Planning, coordination and running of program	X	
	Medication stock management system	X	
	Supervision of personnel and patient tracking	X	
	Information technology	X	
	Obligatory testing of HIV (not VCT)	X	
	Drug resistance vigilance	X	
	Serologic vigilance	X	
Enabling environment	Strategic communication	X	
	Community development and environment improving to reduce vulnerability (total, not broken up by intervention)	X	
	Institutional development directly related to AIDS	X	
	Human rights program	X	
	Specific programs about AIDS aimed at women	X	
	Programs to reduce gender-based violence	X	
Orphans and vulnerable children	Community support	X	
	Support for families/homes for orphans and vulnerable children	X	
	Institutional care	X	
	Basic medical care for orphans and vulnerable children	X	
	Education for orphans and vulnerable children	X	
	Universal precautions	X	
	Services for orphans and vulnerable children (total)	X	
	Social services and administrative costs	X	
HIV Research	Biomedical research	X	
	Social science research	X	
	Clinical research	X	
	Epidemiological research	X	
	Total research about HIV	X	
	Vaccine research	X	
Prevention	Prevention activities, total	X	
	Male circumcision	X	
	Communication about health topics for social and behavior change	X	
	Voluntary testing and counseling	X	
	Safe medical injections	X	
	Safe medical injections	X	
	Social marketing of condoms	X	
	Microbicides	X	
	Community mobilization	X	
	Universal precautions	X	
	Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of STIs	X	
	Post-exposure prophylaxis	X	
	Workplace prevention programs	X	
	Programs to reduce harm for injecting drug users	X	
	Condom provision for men in the public and private sectors	X	
	Condom provision for women in the public and private sectors	X	
	Risk reduction in vulnerable communities	X	
Social protection and social service	Income generation	X	
	Social protection through monetary benefits	X	
	Social protection through delivery of social services	X	
	Social protection through delivery of goods	X	
	Social protection and social services, total	X	
Human	Formative education	X	

Spending category	Spending item	PLWHA growth rate	Total population growth rate
resources	Training	X	
	Monetary incentives for human resources	X	
	Human resources, total	X	
Treatment	Other caring and treatment services, total	X	
	Hospital treatment, total	X	
	Transport of patients and emergency rescue	X	
	Treatment of opportunistic infections	X	
Total		X	

X indicates that the variable was used to determine the cost of the intervention.
Source: NASA Guatemala 2010-Consultants

Projection scenarios: the following table describes the 3 demand and 3 supply scenarios projected in the model. The Base Scenario most closely resembles the current circumstances and reflects existing information about future costs and funding commitments by government and donors. It also assumes that the country will be able to reach its coverage targets by 2015 and that these targets will remain constant afterwards.

On the demand side, the Efficiency Scenario assumes that there are cost savings resulting from both economies of scale in the purchasing of ARVs and improved management (see Box 1). The Lower Coverage Scenario assumes that universal coverage is not reached until 2023, instead of 2015 (in the Base and Efficiency scenarios). Hence, the relationship between the magnitudes of the resources demanded in the three scenarios is as follows:

Base Scenario > Efficiency Scenario > Lower Coverage Scenario

On the supply side the Optimistic Scenario assumes that both government and donors increase their funding relative to the Base Scenario while household spending grows in tandem with GNI. The Pessimistic Scenario assumes that future funding from government and households will be smaller than in the two preceding scenarios while funding from donors will drop to zero after 2015. Thus, the relationship between the magnitudes of the resources supplied in the three scenarios is as follows:

Optimistic Scenario > Base Scenario > Pessimistic Scenario

From the above formulation of scenarios, it follows that the combination of scenarios that will produce the biggest gap in funding will be the Base Demand Scenario combined with the Pessimistic Supply Scenario. Conversely, the combination that will yield the smallest gap will be the Lower Coverage Demand Scenario combined with the Optimistic Supply Scenario.

Box 1: Management costs of HIV/AIDS programs in the LAC region

In 2008, management costs were below 7 percent for all countries in the region, with the exception of Guatemala, where they represented 15 percent, and the Dominican Republic, where they accounted for more than one-fourth of all HIV/AIDS resources. In Ecuador, management costs were 5 percent of total HIV/AIDS spending, in line with most countries in the region. Still, there were countries in the region, such as Cuba, Costa Rica, Colombia, and Panama, that managed to devote as little as 1 percent of their costs to management. It is important to understand why Guatemala and the Dominican Republic had such a high management burden and to unveil the mechanisms that may enable those two countries to improve program efficiency by reducing their management spending.

Figure 16 Expenditure comparisons between Guatemala and Latin America and Caribbean countries, circa 2008

Source: Authors from UNAIDS 2010 (www.unaids.org) and World Bank 2010 (www.worldbank.org).

Figure 17 Demand and supply scenarios

Demand scenarios		Supply scenarios		
D1 (Base)	Reach universal coverage for all interventions by 2015 and maintain this coverage through 2023	S1 (Base)	Public sources	Remains constant as a percentage of GNI through 2023
			Households	Annual out-of-pocket spending by households is projected such that average spending per PLWHA remains constant and equal to its observed 2008 value
			Donors	Current funding commitments by donors are kept through 2015 then this funding category drops in a linear fashion to become 0 in the year 2023
D2 (Efficiency)	Same coverage assumptions as in D1 but in addition there is a projected reduction in costs from efficiency measures in management and ARV costs	S2 (Optimistic)	Public sources	Remains constant as a percentage of GNI through 2015, then grows progressively to double in percentage in 2023
			Households	Household out-of-pocket spending grows at the same rate as the GNI
			Donors	They preserve the current funding unaltered in absolute, real terms through 2023
D3 (Lower Coverage)	Reach universal coverage by 2023 and no cost-efficiency measures	S3 (Pessimistic)	Public sources	Future GNI growth, beyond 2008, is supposed to be the lowest growth observed in the preceding three years, 2006-2008
			Households	Annual out-of-pocket spending by households is projected such that average spending per PLWHA remains constant and equal to its lowest observed value in the period 2006-2008
			Donors	Beyond 2015 donor funding drops to 0

5.3. Gap calculation

In any given year there is projected financing gap if demand and supply of resources differ. If demand is greater than supply, there is a deficit in financing and new sources of funding or measures to reduce costs are required; if supply is greater than demand there is a financing surplus, in which case one or more funding levels can be reduced or interventions can be expanded. The full gap projection model is shown below in Figure 19.

Figure 18 Demand, supply and gap scenarios

Figure 19 Projection model for establishing future financing gaps

6. Sources of information

This study used multiple sources of information for demography, epidemiology, economic growth, costs, funding, etc. The sources include Guatemala's National Institute of Statistics (INE), and the Central Bank, the OECD Health Data, the Ministry of Health's MOH, HIV/AIDS program, the NASA reports 2010, the UNGASS report 2008-2009, and information provided by experts. The exact data source used is shown in a note under each table and figure in this report.

7. Results

7.1. Evolution of the epidemic

In its base scenario the model projects a growing number of total HIV/AIDS cases in Guatemala. Over the 15 year period shown in Table 8, the number of cases will increase from 37,132 to 42,038, or 13 percent total increase (equivalent to an annual average growth rate of 0.86 percent). The table also shows that the rate of under-reporting, initially at 71 percent in 2008, is expected to drop continuously through 2023, to reach a value of 37.9 percent. This projection is the result of a simple, yet empirically unsubstantiated assumption: that each year the absolute number of reported cases equals that of the previous year plus 5 percent of the previous year's under-reported cases. In other words, it is assumed that under-reporting is absorbed into the reported cases at a constant annual rate of 5 percent. Figure 20 graphically presents the information contained in the table below.

Table 8 Projected evolution of the HIV/AIDS epidemic, 2008-2023

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Total cases (C)	60.243	60.936	61.456	61.930	62.367	62.771	63.147	63.498	63.829	64.141	64.435	64.715	64.981	65.235	65.477	65.709
Reported cases (R)	15.265	17.233	19.185	21.096	22.870	24.641	26.345	27.917	29.492	31.005	32.460	33.794	35.139	36.433	37.679	38.878
Under-reported cases (U)	44.978	43.703	42.271	40.834	39.496	38.129	36.802	35.581	34.337	33.135	31.975	30.921	29.842	28.801	27.798	26.831
Under-reporting rate (%)	4,7%	1,7%	8,8%	5,9%	3,3%	0,7%	8,3%	6,0%	3,8%	1,7%	9,6%	7,8%	5,9%	4,2%	2,5%	0,8%

Annual absorption rate of under-reporting: 5%.

Figure 20 HIV/AIDS cases: total, reported, under-reported and under-reporting rate, 2008-2023 (number and percentage)

The following figure shows the expected consequence of a change in the ARV administration criterion. As can be seen, the combined effect of the ARV policy (both the CD4 count and its coverage) is a net drop in the projected number of PLWHA.

Figure 21 Simulation of the effect of a change in the criterion for ARV therapy on the projected number and prevalence of HIV/AIDS cases, 2008-2023 (cases and percent)

Further epidemiological information is presented in Table 9 for the Base Scenario. It includes the PLWHA and the projected prevalence if the ARV policy remained unchanged, then the same variables with a more aggressive ARV policy, the expected number of annual deaths, the mortality rate among the PLWHA, the persons in need of ARV therapy and, finally, those receiving the therapy.

7.2. Spending projections

Spending projections for the Base Demand Scenario are presented in Table 10. With the exception of the last spending category shown, “Other”, all other categories are those that in 2008 represented more than 1 percent of total spending in 2008. Together they accounted for 95 percent of total spending. The category “Other” lumps together all other spending items, which in 2008 amounted to about 5 percent of total spending.

According to the Base Demand Scenario, annual HIV/AIDS spending is expected to grow from US\$ 51.3 million in 2008 to US\$ 264.4 million in 2023, nearly a 415 percent increase. The projected spending share for the 7 largest spending categories is shown below in Figure 22.

Figure 22 Base Demand Scenario: Projected spending shares year 2023 (percent)

The above projections imply that total HIV/AIDS spending in the country will increase, both per citizen and per PLWHA (Figure 23). In 2008, these respective figures were US\$3.75 and US\$ 62.1. The model projects that by the year 2023 they will be US\$ 13.76 and US\$ 214.

Figure 23 Projected spending on HIV/AIDS, per citizen and per PLWHA, 2008-2023 (real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Table 9 Epidemiological and treatment coverage historic information, 2000-2008, and projections, 2009-2023 (numbers and percentages)

	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	
Population (million)	11.2	11.5	11.8	12.1	12.4	12.7	13.0	13.4	13.7	14.0	14.4	14.7	15.1	15.5	15.8	16.2	16.6	16.9	17.3	17.7	18.1	18.5	18.8	19.2	
PLWHA (thousand)	48.0	52.0	55.0	56.0	58.0	58.0	59.0	59.0	60.2	60.9	61.5	61.9	62.4	62.8	63.1	63.5	63.8	64.1	64.4	64.7	65.0	65.2	65.5	65.7	
Prevalence (%)	0.43	0.45	0.47	0.46	0.47	0.46	0.45	0.44	0.44	0.43	0.43	0.42	0.41	0.41	0.40	0.39	0.39	0.38	0.37	0.37	0.36	0.35	0.35	0.34	
PLWHA after ARV treatment effect (thousand)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	60.2	60.8	61.3	61.8	62.2	62.5	62.8	63.1	63.3	63.5	63.7	63.8	63.9	64.0	64.0	63.9
Prevalence after ARV treatment effect (%)										0.44	0.44	0.43	0.42	0.41	0.41	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.38	0.37	0.36	0.36	0.35	0.34	0.33
Newly reported HIV/AIDS cases										15.3	17.2	19.2	21.1	22.9	24.6	26.3	27.9	29.5	31.0	32.5	33.8	35.1	36.4	37.7	38.9
Deaths from HIV/AIDS		2.900	3.500	4.000	4.600	4.100	3.950	3.900	3.499	3.495	3.493	3.493	3.489	3.489	3.489	3.486	3.486	3.487	3.487	3.484	3.484	3.485	3.486	3.487	
Mortality rate among PLWHA (%)		5.58	6.36	7.14	7.93	7.07	6.69	6.61	5.81	5.73	5.68	5.64	5.59	5.56	5.53	5.49	5.46	5.44	5.41	5.38	5.36	5.34	5.32	5.31	
Persons in need of ARV therapy (thousands)		7.8	9.6	11.4	13.1	14.6	19.0	20.9	19.8	21.3	22.7	24.2	25.6	27.0	28.4	29.8	31.3	32.7	32.9	33.0	33.1	33.3	33.4	33.5	
Persons receiving ARV therapy (thousands)							5.8	8.6	-	13.3	21.6	22.9	24.3	25.6	27.0	28.3	29.7	31.1	31.2	31.4	31.5	31.6	31.7	31.8	

Table 10 Demand for funding: Base Scenario with detailed costing information for largest cost items, 2008-2023 (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Expense	Spending category	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Administrati on and program managemen t	Planning, coordination and program management	2.2	2.6	3.0	3.6	4.3	5.1	6.0	7.1	7.5	7.7	7.8	8.0	8.2	8.5	8.7	8.8
	Infrastructure improvement and construction	1.5	1.8	2.1	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.2	4.9	5.2	5.5	5.7	6.0	6.2	6.4	6.7	6.9
	Administration and transaction costs associated with the management of funds	1.3	1.6	1.9	2.2	2.6	3.1	3.7	4.4	4.6	4.9	5.1	5.3	5.5	5.7	5.9	6.1
	Monitoring and evaluation	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.8	2.1	2.5	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.1	3.2	3.3	3.4	3.5
Prevention	Prevention of transmission of mother to child	1.9	2.2	2.5	2.8	3.3	3.7	4.3	4.9	5.2	5.5	5.7	6.0	6.2	6.4	6.6	6.8
	Communication about health topics for social and behavior change	1.8	2.1	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.2	4.9	5.8	6.0	6.1	6.2	6.4	6.5	6.6	6.8	6.9
	Programs for sex workers and their clients	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.0
	Risk reduction for vulnerable populations	1.6	1.9	2.2	2.6	3.1	3.7	4.4	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.7	5.8	5.9	6.0	6.1
	Social marketing of condoms	1.5	1.8	2.1	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.2	4.9	5.1	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.5	5.6	5.8	5.9
	Blood safety	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.4
	Prevention of HIV transmission for persons living with HIV	0.7	0.9	1.1	1.4	1.8	2.3	2.9	3.7	3.9	4.1	4.3	4.4	4.6	4.8	5.0	5.1
	Programs for men who have sex with men	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	1.0
	Prevention, diagnosis and treatment of STIs	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.9	1.0	1.2	1.5	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.0	2.0	2.1
Treatment and care	Adult ARV therapy, all lines	9.2	9.6	10.1	11.9	14.1	16.7	19.8	20.7	21.9	21.9	22.9	23.8	24.7	25.6	26.4	27.3
	Treatment of opportunistic infections	8.0	9.5	11.3	13.3	15.8	18.7	22.2	26.2	27.7	27.7	29.0	30.2	31.3	32.4	33.5	34.6
	Hospital care, total	6.4	7.6	9.0	10.6	12.6	14.9	17.6	20.9	22.0	22.0	23.1	24.0	24.9	25.8	26.6	27.5
	Ambulatory patients	6.2	6.5	6.8	8.1	9.6	11.4	13.4	14.1	14.9	15.6	16.4	17.0	17.6	18.3	18.9	19.5
	Other treatment and care services, total	1.0	1.2	1.4	1.7	2.0	2.3	2.8	3.3	3.5	3.5	3.6	3.8	3.9	4.0	4.2	4.3
	First-line ARV therapy	0.9	3.6	15.1	16.0	16.9	17.9	18.8	19.8	20.2	20.5	19.9	19.4	18.8	18.9	19.0	19.0

Other	4.5	7.4	27.4	29.9	32.8	36.1	40.3	45.5	47.6	49.7	50.5	51.2	52.0	52.6	53.1	53.7
Total	51.3	60.1	87.1	100.1	115.4	133.4	155.0	176.2	185.0	189.6	196.2	202.4	208.3	214.0	219.6	225.1

Table 11 Supply of funding: Base scenario, 2008-2023. (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Sources		2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Public sources	Central Government contribution	12,9	12,9	13,6	14,3	15,0	15,7	16,5	17,4	18,3	19,2	20,2	21,2	22,2	23,4	24,5	25,7
	Mandatory employer social security contributions	11,1	11,1	11,7	12,2	12,9	13,5	14,2	14,9	15,7	16,5	17,3	18,2	19,1	20,1	21,1	22,1
	Mandatory employee social security contributions	5,0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total public sources		29,0	24,0	25,2	26,5	27,9	29,3	30,8	32,3	34,0	35,7	37,5	39,4	41,3	43,4	45,6	47,8
Private sources	Household expenditures	3,9	4,0	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,1	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,1
Total private sources		3,9	4,0	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,1	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,1	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,1
International sources	Government of the Netherlands	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	Government of the United States	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	2,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	The Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria	11,9	11,9	11,9	11,9	11,9	11,9	11,9	11,9	11,9	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	UNAIDS	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF)	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	Caritas International / Catholic Relief Services	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, and National Red Cross Societies	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	Plan International	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	International non-profit organizations and foundations not classified above	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,9	1,9	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Total international sources		18,4	18,4	18,4	18,4	18,4	18,4	18,4	18,4	18,4	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
TOTAL		51,3	46,4	47,6	48,9	50,3	51,7	53,2	54,8	56,5	40,0	41,6	43,6	45,5	47,6	49,7	52,0

Table 12 Demand and supply scenarios, 2009-2023 (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Demand															
D1	60.1	87.1	100.1	115.4	133.4	155.0	176.2	185.0	189.6	196.2	202.4	208.3	214.0	219.6	225.1
D2	60.2	86.2	99.4	113.1	129.3	148.7	167.5	176.3	180.6	186.7	192.6	198.2	203.4	208.7	213.9
D3	53.5	56.9	60.7	64.7	69.1	73.9	79.1	84.9	91.1	98.0	105.5	113.8	122.9	133.0	144.2
Supply															
O1	46.4	47.6	48.9	50.3	51.7	53.2	54.8	56.5	40.0	41.6	43.6	45.5	47.6	49.7	52.0
O2	47.6	48.9	50.3	51.7	53.2	54.8	56.5	62.0	67.8	74.4	81.8	90.4	100.1	111.2	123.8
O3	39.8	40.7	41.7	42.7	43.7	44.8	46.0	28.8	30.0	31.3	32.8	34.2	35.7	37.2	38.8

In the Base Scenario there is a considerable and growing future financing gap as is shown in the following figure. By the year 2015 it will amount to US\$ 121.3 million and by the year 2023 it will have grown to US\$ 173.0 million. In 2015 the gap will represent exactly 80 percent of total projected spending (US\$ 185 million, see Table 10).

Figure 24 Base Scenario: Projected gap between demand and supply of funding for HIV/AIDS, 2009-2023 (million real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

But the funding picture could be much worse as is shown in the following table which combines all scenarios to produce 9 gap calculations for each of three years 2009, 2015 and 2023. As anticipated, the largest gap occurs when combining the Base Demand Scenario (D1) with the Pessimistic Supply Scenario (S3). By 2015 the gap would be US\$ 101.3 million and by 2023 it would grow to US\$ 186.3 million. The smallest gap scenarios are those that result from combining the Lower Coverage Demand Scenario (D3) with the Optimistic Supply Scenario (S2).

Table 13 Gap calculations. 2009, 2015, and 2023 (million of real US\$ of Dec. 2008)

Demand scenarios	Supply scenarios								
	2009			2015			2023		
	S1 Base	S2 Optimistic	S3 Pessimistic	S1 Base	S2 Optimistic	S3 Pessimistic	S1 Base	S2 Optimistic	S3 Pessimistic
D1 Base	-13.7	-12.5	-20.3	-121.4	-119.7	-130.2	-173.1	-101.3	-186.3
D2 Efficiency	-13.8	-12.6	-20.4	-86.1	-84.4	-94.9	-161.9	-90.1	-175.1
D3 Lower Coverage	-7.1	-5.9	-13.7	-24.3	-22.7	-33.2	-92.2	-20.4	-105.4

8. Findings from the workshop

8.1. First Workshop

In order to share and validate results with key local players, a workshop was arranged by UNAIDS, and held on September 3, 2010. The participants were representatives of leading

organizations in the national response: the National AIDS Program, Social Security, USAID, CDC, several UN cooperation agencies, NGOs working on AIDS, Human Rights Office, Sexual Diversity, Transgender and PLWHA associations (Annex 1).

The workshop began with a welcome address by the UNAIDS Representative in Guatemala, Dr Enrique Zelaya, who put in context the efforts of thinking about the future of health financing and devising sustainability strategies to maintain and expand the response to AIDS.

Then, the rationale and methodology of the study was presented to the audience. After a short exchange, the key findings, preliminary conclusions and recommendations were also presented. In the next segment, the floor was open to questions and comments about the model, the results and alternative sources of financing for the years to come.

Several positive comments were made about the model. Participants recommended UNAIDS continue providing technical assistance for the country to take full advantage of the model during the new strategic plan (2011-2016) formulation process. It was also proposed to use the projection results for resource advocacy from public and private sources.

There were also critiques of the model, falling into three types: a) those addressing the lack of qualitative variables to grasp contextual features of the country, such as ethnicity, rurality and geographical accessibility, and changes in public policy and staff rotation with each new government administration; b) those confronting the model's figures with most recent NASA results for 2007-8, relative to expenditures in PLWHA; c) those complaining because MOH authorities and financial officers did not attend the workshop.

In order to increase sustainability, at least three kinds of suggestions were made: a) engaging the private sector, in partnership with the Guatemalan Social Security Institute (IGSS), to establish AIDS policies in the workplace, as the business community is aware of the potential costs of AIDS for businesses; b) improving the local capacities to analyze data and build persuasive discourses based on health economics tools and concepts; c) to strengthen a multisectoral approach in responding to HIV/AIDS, because the best way to deal with increasing costs of the epidemic is containing transmission and providing earlier detection.

8.2. Second Workshop

Due to a national holiday for health workers, as well as a meeting with Global Fund officers, MOH representatives did not attend the validation workshop. After an interview with the Viceminister of Health, Dr Pedro Rosales, a new workshop was arranged by UNAIDS and held on October 7, 2010.

The Director of Health Care Programs presided over the event. There were also representatives of the National AIDS Program, General Management Office, Budget Department, National AIDS Spending Assessment (NASA) coordinator, and Health Care Integrated System (SIAS).

The UNAIDS Representative gave the introductory speech, covering background issues on Guatemala's efforts to cope with the AIDS epidemics, the pressure over resources in recent years, and the importance of using scenarios as a tool to identify sustainability strategies, not only to confront AIDS, but for all health and social expenditures.

The rationale, methodology, results and conclusions were presented and discussed with the participants. It included two new resource availability scenarios: the effect of maintaining Global Fund support until 2023, and the effect of the Government assuming as a financial responsibility and public policy the commitment to universal access.

The comments received referred to the cultural and social elements of the transmission and care seeking behavior, which seems not to be present in the statistical model, and yet they are important enough not to be dismissed. The indigenous population and rural areas of the country were mentioned as opaque areas where few cases are reported but it is in part a result of the limited coverage and response capacity installed in those areas.

Other issues about the projections emerged, as the MOH is confronting a serious lack of resources to end the fiscal year, and AIDS seems not to be as much a priority at the moment when compared with basic services and hospital demands that are at risk of not being funded. The positive part of that comment was that tools such as this should be applied to other high cost conditions demanding a large percentage of MOH expenditures including chronic conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, and obesity, accidents and violence, among others. A more realistic projection of financial needs would help facilitate a more informed and persuasive negotiation with the Ministry of Finance, Congress of the Republic and Business Chambers.

The possibilities of the MOH assuming the costs of expanding services for universal access were assessed as unlikely, but with a caveat: it was acknowledged that AIDS-related organizations have shown more assertiveness and advocacy skills, thus resulting in an increasing public budget for AIDS, even in difficult times.

Finally, the participants made positive comments about the effort and thanked UNAIDS for their support and the possibility of ongoing discussions about the future of health financing, for AIDS and also a broader set of programmes and services.

9. Conclusions

This study built a model to project the future demand for and supply of funding for HIV/AIDS national response interventions and to determine whether there will be funding gaps. The demand for funding is expected to grow, challenging Guatemala to improve coverage for preventive and curative care for HIV/AIDS in order to meet the MDGs. An expected drop in external funding further complicates this challenge.

The study reveals that the effort made by the Guatemalan government to strengthen the social public services is essential for covering the future growth in demand. The political will to support the health sector and in particular HIV/AIDS interventions made it possible to obtain positive gaps demonstrating the importance of public funding. The question is whether or not this effort will become sustainable and if public policy will be enacted to ensure that funds are linked with current expenditure.

A projection of future demand and supply of funding reveals that in several of the projected scenarios a large funding gap is expected. New sources of funding, such as growing fiscal effort by government, or sustained or greater financial support, will be needed to bridge the projected gaps.

Annex A: Workshop Participants List

Name	Organization
United Nations System	
José Enrique Zelaya	UNAIDS
Patricia Rivera	UNAIDS
Fernando Amado	PAHO/WHO
Andrés Alonso	UNDP
Gilda Rivas	UNFPA
Juan Fernando Díaz Suchini	UNESCO
Bilateral Cooperation Agencies and Projects	
Lucrecia Castillo	USAID
Fernando Cano	USAID / PASCA
Jorge Berger	USAID / AIDSTAR 2
Sandra Juárez	CDC / GAP
Ericka Stolz	CDC / PROVIT
Andrea Scheldtorf	Doctors without Borders / Switzerland
Víctor Hugo Fernández	Sida i Societat Barcelona / Spain
AIDS Organizations	
Iris López	National AIDS Commission / MOH
Jorge Ágreda	Country Coordinating Mechanism
Saira Ortega	Asociación Salud Integral (ASI)
Herbert Hernández	Proyecto Unidos / ASI
Carlos Valdéz	Proyecto Unidos / ASI
Margarita Yoc	ASECSA
Hugo R Valladares	Asociación Gente Nueva (PLWHA)
Carlos Duanerd	Sexual Diversity Network
Oscar Morales	Human Rights Office